

Models for Living Lab's sustainability. Evidences from Italy and the Netherlands

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Abstract

Living Lab is either part of, or constitutes an Innovation Network of people, private firms and public institutions. The Living Lab has the potential to convey value to the entire network but it requires the support and commitment of its stakeholders to operate at full regime and ensure long term viability. For this reason, financial sustainability is one of the main challenges for any Living Lab. With the current paper, the objective is to understand how long-term viability can be reached through a sustainable business model based on the right collaboration mode in a multi-stakeholder environment. This research proposes a theoretical framework in which is stressed the importance for the Living Lab of the innovation network and of the creation and demonstration of value to the stakeholders. Then, based on this framework, three practical cases are analyzed: Stratumseind Living Lab in Eindhoven, the AUAS field labs in Amsterdam and the ARCA Textile and Clothing Living Lab in Palermo. From the observation of the three Living Lab, this paper proposes a distinction between product-oriented and policy-oriented Living Lab and presents some meaningful implications of the two approaches to sustainability.

Keywords: *Living Lab, Sustainability, Innovation Network, Value creation, Social Innovation, Stakeholder Commitment.*

1 Introduction and objectives

Living Lab is either part of, or constitutes an innovation network of people, private firms and public institutions based on knowledge and observation, and guided by a practice driven approach to co-creation. The entire ecosystem built around the Living Lab concurs in the realization and implementation of user- or community-driven innovative solutions. The Living Lab conveys value to the entire network but it requires the support and commitment of several stakeholders to operate at full regime and ensure long term viability. Indeed, sustainability is a key challenge for any Living Lab. Building mutual trust and identifying a set of shared objectives with the actors of the surrounding ecosystem is crucial for the sustainability and success of the Living Lab. To this purpose, it's not sufficient that the Living Lab creates value, but it must also demonstrate it across the network, and make both methods and results tangible to every innovation partner. For this reason, it's fundamental for a Living Lab to deeply understand its network and a comprehensive multi-stakeholder analysis is necessary to identify the way to produce value and deliver it to each actor.

This paper has the objective to identify the strategies developed by three different Living Labs to address the problem of sustainability: Stratumseind Living Lab (SLL) in Eindhoven, AUAS field labs in Amsterdam and Textile and Clothing Living Lab (TECLA) in Palermo. Creating an economically viable Living Lab means aligning internally consistent processes with the needs of external stakeholders so that revenues are generated and funding are ensured (Katzy, 2012). This research investigates the relationship between Living Lab's activities, innovation network, value creation, delivery and demonstration to the stakeholders. Developing a clear view over the complex interrelations among the several actors is fundamental to understand the mechanisms that allow a Living Lab to generate revenues and thus ensure sustainability.

2 Literature framework

Living Lab as an innovation network

The concept of innovation network is crucial to understand Living Lab. In fact, Living Lab is not only a network of infrastructures but especially a network of people with their experiences. (Mulder, 2008). The Living Lab indeed serves as connection between research, citizens and the actual living environment (Franz, 2014). Living Lab is a network of different stakeholders in which the existing relationships are supported, while it's given the opportunity to new partners to meet and collaborate to develop new products and services (Bergvall-Kåreborn et al., 2009). The Living Lab

has a role of innovation intermediary in a complex network of different stakeholders: it functions as an aggregator of various external inputs that are then translated into requirements and design parameters for valuable social innovation (Mention & Torkkeli, 2015; Almirall & Wareham, 2011).

Living Lab is a form of Public-Private-People Partnerships (PPPP) in which, not only users and producers, but also many other heterogeneous stakeholders, such as firms, public agencies, universities, and institutes build an innovation network and collaborate at the creation, prototyping, testing and evaluation of new products and services (Leminen et al, 2012; Niitamo et al., 2006).

Finally, it's important to notice that the innovation network around the Living Lab is constituted of parties with different backgrounds and interests; moreover, these stakeholders often come from a history of interrelations in which roles and expectations are already defined (Eskelinen et al., 2015). The elements above stress the importance for a Living Lab to understanding the complex nature and the dynamics of the innovation network to be able to develop adequate context-specific strategies.

The need for Sustainability

Sustainability is crucial for future feasibility of Living Lab. A significant number of Living Labs present an unintended temporary nature since they stop their activities when the funding ends (Leminen et al., 2012). Many researchers advocate for developing a strong model based on long-term strategy and suggest that a more detailed analysis of this aspect is required (Bergvall-Kareborn et al, 2009; Mastelic et al., 2015)

Sustainability, in the context of Living Lab, refers to two aspects (Bergvall-Kareborn et al, 2009). First, it's considered viability as a pure economical aspect. It refers to the possibility to finance every-day activities, and have the financial availability to provide a service respecting the planned standard. The second aspect is the Living Lab's responsibility to its wider community. This quality must be supported and ensured during the entire life of a Living Lab. Thus, it's fundamental for a Living Lab, not only to sustain economically its activities, but also to continuously expand its network and strengthen the partnerships with crucial sources of innovation and knowledge.

Living Lab's outcome

If the Living Lab is adequately financed overtime, its activities allow the several stakeholders to benefit from:

- *Valorization of knowledge*: several research components of Living Lab allow the transformation of knowledge into models, methods and theories (Bergval-

Kareborn et al., 2009; Veeckman et al., 2013). New products, services and policies can be developed based on this knowledge generated.

- *Exploitation of network*: through the interaction inside a Living Lab, every actor can draw from a wide range of competences and combine disparate sources of knowledge to implement better products and services. Therefore, every partner is an added value for the network and at the same time can benefit from it (Veeckman et al., 2013).
- *Social impact*: The output of the development process is a product or a service which, not only brings a direct economic benefit to the commissioner, but also improves living conditions and the social environment.

Value creation

It's evident that the value delivered by Living Lab varies in terms of nature, effected actors and implications. Thus, this research provides a classification of value into three different categories:

- *Economic Value* covers economic metrics that are highly tangible from different stakeholders' perspectives (Baccarne et al., 2014). Thus, these results can be assessed and evaluated from an economical perspective. (Bergvall-Kareborn, 2009)
- Economic value can be extended to include other forms of value such as employee value, customer value, supplier value, managerial value and societal value (Bergvall-Kareborn, 2009). This is referred as *Business Value*. The generated business value can bring relevant benefits to the various actors of the innovation ecosystem.
- Finally, *Public Value* is delivered by Living Lab when it supports and promote the implementation of solutions that respond to local challenges and opportunities, and contribute to the achievement of public policies (Cosgrave & Tryphonas, 2012).

3 Research questions

The literature framework developed in the previous section constitutes a starting point for researching how Living Lab should address the challenge of financial sustainability.

The framework shows that the activities of the Living Lab produce a certain outcome which translates in three different categories of value. The process of value creation is enabled only if there is complete commitment by all the actors of the Living Lab's innovation network. Literature advocates for the development of a business model that can ensure financial sustainability. This paper wants to contribute to current research by investigating in practice what different Living Labs do to reach sustainability. In particular, this research focuses on how the nature of the network is linked to the outcome of the Living Lab, and how the Living Lab creates and demonstrates value to its stakeholders.

Consequently, the following section of this study are guided by the following research questions:

- *Which stakeholders constitute the network of the Living Lab and how do they participate to the outcome of the Living Lab?*
- *What kind of value does the Living Lab create and how is the value delivered and demonstrated to each stakeholder?*
- *Which business model, forms of funding, and other revenue streams ensure Living Lab's sustainability?*

4 Methodology

The chosen research strategy is a general discussion of a more detailed case study. The adequateness of this method was analysed according to the principles expressed by Yin (2003). For the purposes of this research, three successful cases are analysed in detail: Stratumseind Living Lab and AUAS field labs represent two valuable examples that reached a phase of maturity. Despite operating with diametrically opposed strategies, they developed a sustainable business model, which ensures long-term viability and allows them to have a concrete impact in the innovation ecosystem and in the wider society. Then, it's presented ARCA Textile and Clothing Living Lab which is still in a start-up phase. For each case, it's first provided a short overview and contextualization. Then, it's described their innovation network. Finally, it's presented the way they deliver economic, business and public value to their stakeholders, and how this value is translated in findings and revenue streams. The information was collected through qualitative methods: interviews with several stakeholders, observation of daily activities directly on the field, and specific presentations.

5 Empirical research

Stratumseind Living Lab

Context The municipality of Eindhoven in the last years developed various living lab initiatives with the support of several actors from diverse sectors. SLL, which is part of the Stratumseind 2.0 & Smart City project, is one of the most successful examples. Stratumseind is a pub street about 300 meters long that hosts around 50 pubs in the centre of Eindhoven. Every week more than 20.000 visitors enjoy the nightlife but also around 800 incidents a year are recorded.

Description SLL is an instrument to measure the influence that can be created on behaviour through the application of diverse solution based on light, fragrance and design. The Living Lab is a test facility for new sensors, data harvesting, privacy, smart interfaces, smart lighting systems, design and gaming.

Challenge The mission of SLL is to support companies and institutions in the development of innovative products, services and policies which can structurally improve the economic and social functioning on the Stratumseind.

Network Thanks to the highly technological content and to fervid innovation environment of Eindhoven, SLL involves a massive number of partners.

- Governmental institutions: SLL involves local administrations such as the municipality of Eindhoven, Tilburg and the province of Noord-Brabant; public organizations, like the Police Department; also, other Public-Private-People-Partnerships (PPPPs) like Brainport Eindhoven, which is a triple helix collaboration.
- Educational institutions: The Eindhoven University of Technology represents one of the main sources of knowledge, but several other universities, not only from the region, are involved to a different degree.
- Businesses: many private companies take part to the activities of SLL. The degree of maturity of such organizations is various: technological start-ups as well as multinational companies, can find the right compromise to use the services of the Living Lab.
- Citizens: The involvement of the citizens is mainly passive. In fact, they serve the Lab as a subject to observe. In addition, they allow experimentation and evaluation of new technologies. The vast majority of the observed citizens, isn't aware to be part of the Living Lab.

Outcome SLL facilitates the combination of knowledge, experience, competences and technologies of different actors to develop better co-created products and services. The resulting new products, services and policies not only have substantial competitive advantages, but also improve living conditions in Stratumseind.

Value creation Economic value is delivered to private businesses and organizations which can ideate better products and services. Business value is delivered to companies and organizations which benefit from the experience of the SLL and of the other parties. They gain new knowledge, establish relationships with research institutions and improve their business model and innovation capacity. Public value is delivered to governmental institutions that obtain the knowledge necessary for the development of better policies. Citizens obtain a safer and more liveable street for nightlife.

Funding and revenue SLL began by a small funding by the municipality of Eindhoven, then it obtained subsidies at provincial and national level, and ensured the support of educational and governmental institutions. That was made possible by the direct involvement of some members of the public administration in the activities. Moreover, the Lab was clearly linked with the concepts of Smart City and social innovation which made the public value more tangible. At the same time, SLL receives economic support by several companies that take advantage of the experience, competences and unique setting of SLL to co-create innovative products. The development of better products is already a direct demonstration of economic and business value. To its business partners, SLL offers different collaboration and payment options based on the maturity of the firm and the objective of the product or service to be developed jointly.

Amsterdam Lab

Context In the last years, the municipality of Amsterdam started an ambitious plan of reorganization with the objective to operate in a “locality-oriented” manner, with a prominent focus on social innovation. Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences (AUAS), together with the city council, has engaged a creative process to address diffused social issues. With this purpose, AUAS as part of its department of Urban Management developed local innovation environments, called “field labs”. In the period 2012-2016 three field labs were established in different neighbourhood of the city: Amsterdam Nieuw-West, Amsterdam Oost and Amsterdam Zuidoost.

Description The three fieldlabs realized several projects with the objective of gaining fundamental knowledge for the solutions of recurrent social problems. The neighbourhood is seen as a local level playing field formed by several already present

actors with their own needs and interests, which get together to translate complex urban issues in context-specific solutions.

Challenge The mission of AUAS fieldlabs is to deliver new governance arrangements and social policies which enable the development of context specific solutions to complex social, sustainability and economic issues that are faced in the city.

The Network AUAS provides an interesting distinction of the main stakeholders between strategic partners and project partners. The project partners participate only to one or few specific initiatives of the fieldlabs while the strategic partners also share the organization of the network of the fieldlabs at a higher level.

- Educational institutions: the AUAS is the owner of the fieldlabs activities and main educational institute involved. Professors, researchers and students from several departments of the university are involved with different roles and responsibilities.
- Governmental institutions: the fieldlabs involve primarily two layers of governmental institutions. The municipality of Amsterdam is the main strategic partner and financier, while the local administrations of the three neighbourhoods that host the fieldlabs are involved in a more operational manner.
- Business: there is a limited number of business involved, mainly as project partners. Only big social associations and utility companies, such as social housing companies, are interested in the knowledge valorised by AUAS fieldlabs.
- Citizens: a sample of citizens is involved in every initiative of the fieldlabs. They're empowered of the role of co-creators of the social innovations and policies resulting from the activities of the fieldlab. Often citizens are involved as associations which are extremely important project partners: in fact, associations represent the needs and perspectives of specific categories of citizens and user groups in a structured manner.

Outcome AUAS fieldlabs allow the application and valorisation of previous knowledge in real-life setting, the development of new knowledge and its combination with different sources. Knowledge can be used by institutions for the development of services and policies.

Value creation Because of the primary interest of the fieldlabs in generating knowledge for the development of social policies, it becomes hard to produce easily sellable solutions. Accordingly, the fieldlabs mainly create public value in the form of knowledge and awareness about diffused social issues and set the bases for future improvements of the urban context. Therefore, the main financiers of the labs are the

governmental and educational institutions which aren't interested in the realization of tangible products but rather in the implementation of innovative social policies. For the fieldlabs it's hard to obtain monetary support from private firms and small businesses. Thus, it's fundamental for AUAS fieldlabs to deliver and demonstrate the generated public value. Accordingly, the process of building trust with every stakeholder is a priority for the fieldlabs. To this extent, AUAS presents research results and concrete suggestions for innovative policies to the municipality and to the University board. AUAS uses a full set of tools and visual supports, such as Value Design Canvas, to help every stakeholder to realize the outcome and potential benefits deriving from the intended learning processes.

Funding and Revenue Every fieldlabs has its own financing scheme. The strategic partners provide a shared budget: It means that no specific project is funded in advance, but the budget must be allocated where needed. In addition to that, other public organization or governmental funds contribute to the fieldlabs budget, while the project partners finance specific initiatives. An ideal scheme of the itemized budget for a single subproject would be financed in equal parts by four categories of actors: AUAS, the urban district, the project partners, and project specific sources. At the moment of research, the AUAS Lab was entering a transition phase to a new positioning with the respect of the municipality of Amsterdam. In fact, thanks to the good results obtained in the experiences of the fieldlabs, AUAS is gaining a stronger position with the central administration of the municipality of Amsterdam.

Textile and Clothing Living Lab

Context TECLA represents one more component to the vivid innovation environment of Palermo, one of South Italy's biggest cities and crucial node of the Mediterranean basin. The Living Lab started in the context of Horizon 2020 Textile & Clothing Business Lab project. TECLA is hosted by Consorzio ARCA which manages a university business incubator and has already ran other Living Labs in Sicily, such as, the Solar Living Lab and Madonie Living Lab.

Description TECLA is an initiative of industrial (micro and small enterprises) development to exploit the endogenous potential of Palermo region reinforcing the innovative capacity of many actors to accelerate the creation of new user-centric solutions. TECLA is a physical space that encourages to discuss ideas and projects, meet partners, develop cooperation methodologies where textile and clothing manufacture meets technologies and advanced multimedia tools. TECLA supports the entire process and the actors involved developing co-creative models for the design of new products and services and linking them with successful business models.

Challenge The main challenge for TECLA is to implement a systemic and integrated approach to local sustainable and inclusive development to reduce the gap between SMEs and research, stimulate entrepreneurship and enlarge the community of artisans. The end objective of TECLA is to foster an integrated co-design approach to produce a lasting impact on the territory.

Network TECLA can count on two main forces in the development of a solid network. On the one hand, it can attract many diverse stakeholders closely linked to the theme of the Living Lab, the textile. On the other hand, it can rely on ARCA and its stakeholders from the quadruple helix.

- Governmental institutions and public organizations: TECLA inherits the innovation ecosystem of ARCA and thus can count on the collaboration of policy makers at regional and municipal level, local development agencies and NGOs. Moreover, TECLA's physical location is inside the community of Cre.Zi. Plus which gathers a broad ecosystem of cultural foundations and public associations. TECLA is also part of TCBL network of labs across Europe.
- Educational institutions: The Consorzio ARCA itself is a partnership between business group and the University of Palermo. In TECLA are involved several professors, researchers and students with different roles and tasks. Minor research institutions are also involved.
- Businesses: TECLA has a strong focus on establishing a concrete partnership across the entire supply chain. To this extent, it involves SMEs and start-ups not only from the textile industry, but also in complementary fields, from IT to design. Family workers and traditional artisans also have a big part in the innovation network.
- Citizens: The citizens are actively engaged in the activities of the Living Lab. User groups, potential entrepreneurs, fashion amateurs, young creatives, members of cultural associations are involved in the activities of the Living Lab through workshops and seminars.

Outcome TECLA supports mutual learning and re-connects the capacities and knowledge of old artisans and fashionistas with the one of the players of the global supply chain, professionals in technology fields, design and fashion students and new entrepreneurs. Thanks to the collaboration of multiple stakeholders and the use of common sophisticated assets the opportunity for new businesses can emerge. Thus,

new employment opportunities and an improved community of artisans can have a positive impact in the region.

Value creation TECLA conveys economic value to private businesses which can ideate better products and services based on new knowledge and advanced technologies. Also, it delivers business value to companies which not only earn new competences, a new co-creation approach and-use shared assets, but also improve their business model. Private companies also get the support of TECLA and create synergies to apply to European programs and financing. Educational institutions become more integrated in the local textile industry and provide students with opportunities for traineeship. Public value is also a main interest for TECLA. There, key social players and innovators are involved to generate environmentally and socially sustainable products, services and processes which fit crucial societal challenges. Moreover, Palermo region suffers of endemic unemployment problems and TECLA's projects can result in new start-ups.

Funding and revenue The Sicilian Living Lab whose funding is from Horizon 2020 TCBL project is located in a territory without large companies and where the public financiers, present in other territorial contexts, don't always respond quickly to the challenges of territorial innovation. Therefore, the sustainability of the Lab necessarily passes through a funding mix given by daily activities, call to action of all the components of the ecosystem and EC funding. TECLA can count on the capacity of ARCA in fund raising, both through its investor network. To demonstrate the public value created TECLA wants to develop a common language and shared understanding of the potential of the Living Lab with its stakeholders, and make explicit these shared values to ensure the support of the main institutional partners. Moreover, TECLA wants to assess the outcome in a measurable way based on traceability of the process, the quality and effectiveness and the relevance of the multi-actor target. The business value created can be accounted and made explicit through ARCA's Open Innovation platform, in which the several partners can be put in the position to generate new links and partnerships, start a new venture or sign R&D contracts and license agreements. The development of better product and services is already a direct demonstration of the economic value generated. Among the other revenue streams on which TECLA can count, it's possible to notice that there is the plan to develop a catalogue of services such as support packages for innovative SMEs, technology transfer methods, access to EU finance, training modules for entrepreneurs, internationalization etc.

6 Observations and Discussion

The two cases from the Netherlands already operated for several years. From their experience it's possible to obtain valuable insights on the relationship between Living Lab's activities, innovation network, value creation and the resulting business model that ensures long term sustainability. These insights are then compared with the strategy developed by TECLA which is still in a start-up phase.

The observations of SLL and the AUAS fieldlabs propose two different declinations of the concept of Living Lab and introduce two prevailing orientations. On one extreme, SLL can be seen as a product-oriented Living Lab in which the outcome is a set of sellable products and services co-created with other companies from a specific industry. On the other extreme, AUAS fieldlabs can be seen as policy-oriented Living Labs in which the outcome is a set of policies co-created with the citizens. The difference between these two models isn't limited to the outcome, but the entire structure of the Living Lab reflects the diverse orientation. In the product-oriented Living Lab the innovation network is highly dynamic and business driven while the user involvement is mainly passive. The focus is on the creation of economic and business value, while public value is more an intended effect rather than a scope. There, the economic and business value is easily demonstrated to the stakeholders which guarantee the sustainability of the Living Lab through direct revenue streams. In the policy-oriented Living Lab the network is more static and institutions driven, while the users are actively involved. The focus is on the creation of public value, while economic and business value is hard to seize. Building mutual trust with key stakeholders is the main option for demonstrating the public value created and ensure adequate funds to the Living Lab.

TECLA represents a promising trade-off between product-orientation and policy-orientation. Indeed, TECLA developed its model as a combination of these elements that can ensure sustainability in a characteristic context like Palermo. To this extent, TECLA identified a particular field of application, the textile industry, which sees the presence of a consistent number of diverse actors that still haven't established important synergies, and where the potential impact of new technologies and innovative business models is still to be exploited. In this context, TECLA aims at enabling the realization of an extremely wide set of sellable products and services, which can translate in substantial revenue streams. At the same time, Palermo region has a strong determination to support initiatives that foster entrepreneurship and employment, valorize traditional craftsmanship and spread concepts such as open innovation and co-creation across the territory. Consequently, TECLA will be able to count on the support of public institutions for additional funds.

7 Results

Analysing the observations collected in the current case study, it's possible to obtain several meaningful insights which answer the research questions. The two approaches presented in the previous section aren't mutually exclusive but rather two extreme positions on the same continuum. Accordingly, the business model which gives the best chances to ensure the necessary funding should be designed starting from the choice of the most suitable positioning in such a continuum. Indeed, determining the right trade-off between product orientation and policy orientation is fundamental to design a Living Lab that can effectively pursue long term sustainability. The adequate trade-off should be determined, not only based on the objective and intended outcome, but especially on the context of application and the surrounding network. In fact, long-term viability is enabled by the funds and revenue streams that can be obtained from the several actors constituting the innovation network. From the case study emerged that the recurrent stakeholders for a Living Lab can be divided in four macro-categories: Governmental Institutions, Educational Institutions, Businesses and Citizens. Two of them are particularly relevant to the purpose of financial sustainability: on the one hand, the presence of a vivid network of businesses and private firms in a specific industry gives the possibility to a Living Lab to focus on the co-creation of new products. On the other hand, if the public institutions share the innovative vision of the Living Lab then it is easier to obtain the needed support for the development of policies and public services. Indeed, based on an exhaustive network analysis a Living Lab should identify the core outcome, and thus the value, to be produced. Finally, the case study provides concrete testimonies on how Living Labs create value (Economic, Business and Public) and how they succeed in delivering it across their innovation network. Indeed, Living Lab should systematically link its outcome and created value with the way of making it tangible to every stakeholder so that an adequate financial return can be ensured.

8 Conclusions

This research suggests that the choice of a suitable business model depends from the context of application: Living Labs with a prevailing orientation towards the product have higher chances to meet sustainability when the chosen theme is central also in the local environment, and thus the Living Lab can count on a large and dynamic network of businesses. In this case, the stakeholders give the necessary financial support when they are capable to seize the Economic and Business value created. Alternatively, more policy-oriented Living Labs require the support of local public institutions. Thus, a policy-oriented Living Lab has better chances to meet sustainability if concepts like social innovation and policy co-development are part of

the strategies of public administration. In this case, it's fundamental to develop trust and a stable relationship with the most strategic stakeholders. Moreover, availability of dedicated public funds and access to European programs and subsidies is another crucial driver for the success of a policy-oriented Living Lab.

9 Limitations and future work

The results present a promising research stream and a novel approach to Living Lab's sustainability, but they are far from being reliable, generalizable and transferable. Therefore, these results require a further validation: the dualism between product- and policy-orientation is inferred by the analysis of only three cases and, to pursue generality and develop an adequate theory, these insights need to be tested on a larger sample of Living Labs. Only via broader mapping it can be eventually possible to apply these findings in different thematic sectors of Living Lab. Moreover, this research was mainly based on qualitative methods, while the employment of quantitative techniques might result in more consistent and robust sets of theories.

References

- Almirall, E., & Wareham, J. (2008) *Living Labs and Open Innovation: Roles and Applicability*. *Electronic Journal for Virtual Organizations and Networks*, 10, pp. 21–46.
- Almirall, E., & Wareham, J. (2011) *Living Labs: Arbiters of Mid- and Ground-Level Innovation*. *Technology Analysis & Strategic Management*, 23(1), pp. 87-102.
- Baccarne, B., Mechant, P., Schuurman, D. (2014) *Empowered Cities? An Analysis of the Structure and Generated Value of the Smart City Ghent*. In R. P. Rosenthal-Sabroux, *Smart City, Progress in IS*. Springer International Publishing, Switzerland .
- Bergvall-Kåreborn, B., Ihlström Eriksson, C., Ståhlbröst, A., Svensson, J. (2009) *A Milieu for Innovation: Defining Living Labs*. *Proceedings of the 2nd ISPIM Innovation Symposium: Simulating Recovery - The Role of Innovation Management*. New York City.
- Cosgrave, E., Tryphonas, T. (2012) *Exploring the Relationship between Smart City Policy and Implementation*. *Proceeding of Smart 2012: The First International Conference On Smart Systems, Devices And Technologies*. Stuttgart, Germany
- Eskelinen, J., Garcia Robles, A., Lindy, I., Marsh, J., Munte-Kunigami, A. (2015). *Citizen-Driven Innovation: A Guidebook for City Mayors and Public Administrators*. World Bank, Washington, DC, and European Network of Living Labs. © World Bank and ENoLL.
- Feurstein, K., Hesmer, A., Hribernik, K. A., Thoben, K. D., Schumacher, J. (2008) *Living Labs – A New Development Strategy*. In Schumacher, J. & Niitamo, V.P. *European Living Labs – A New Approach for Human Centric Regional Innovation*. Wissenschaftlicher, Berlin.
- Franz, Y. (2014) *Chances and Challenges for Social Urban Living Labs in Urban Research*. *Conference Proceedings of Open Living Lab Days 2014*, pp. 105-114.
- Katzy, B. (2012) *Designing Viable Business Models for Living Labs*. *Journal of Organizational Virtualness*, 2(9), pp. 19-24.
- Leminen, S., Westerlund, M., & Kortelainen, M. J. (2012) *A Recipe for Innovation Through Living Lab Networks*. *Proceedings of ISPIM Conferences*
- Mastelic, J., Sahakian, M., Bonazzi, (2015) *How to Keep a Living Lab Alive?* *info*, 17(4), pp. 12-25
- Mention, A.-L., Torkkeli, M. (2015) *Open Innovation: A Multifaceted Perspective*. World Scientific Publishing Company Pte Limited.
- Mulder, I. (2008) *Living Methodologies: Understanding the Social Dynamics of Innovation*. In J. Schumacher, V. Niitamo, *European Living Labs – A New Approach for Human Centric Regional Innovation*, 6, pp. 31-38. Berlin: Wissenschaftlicher Verlag.
- Niitamo, V., Kulkki, S., Eriksson, M., & Hribernik, K. (2006) *State-of-the-art and Good Practice in the Field of Living Labs*. Unpublished
Retrieved from: http://84.88.32.6/openlivinglabs/documents/soa_livinglabs.pdf
- Tukiainen, T., Leminen, S., Westerlund, M. (2015) *Cities as Collaborative Innovation Platforms*. *Technology Innovation Management Review*, 5(10), pp. 16-23.

- Veeckman, K., Schuurman, D., Leminen, S., Lievens, B., Westerlund, M. (2013) *Characteristics and Their Outcomes in Living Labs: A Flemish-Finnish Case Study*. Proceedings of the XXIV ISPIM Conference – Innovating in Global Markets: Challenges for Sustainable Growth. Helsinki, Finland.
- Westerlund, M., Leminen, S. (2011) *Managing the Challenges of Becoming an Open Innovation Company: Experiences from Living Labs*. Technology Innovation Management Review.
- Yin, R. K. (2003). *Case study research: Design and methods*. Thousand Oaks, Calif: Sage Publications.